

A STUDY ON FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT OF GENERATION Y IN KLANG VALLEY, MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT

Employee engagement in Malaysia is among the lowest compared to a few countries in its region. Researchers mentioned that low employee engagement can turn lead to low productivity of employee resulting in organization negativity. Generation Y - those who born between 1980 to 1994; is a generation is that gradually dominating the working industry. Generation Y forms 60% of the current workforce, making them an important asset to businesses all around the world. This research has identified the factors that might influence employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley, Malaysia. Three factors - career growth, work-life balance and corporate social responsibility; were included in this research. Adopting the quantitative approach, a total of 400 questionnaire distributed to the respondents – employed Generation Y that is residing in Klang Valley, Malaysia. The research results show that career growth and work-life balance had influence on employee engagement of Generation Y in Klang Valley, however, corporate social responsibility was found have no influence towards employee engagement. Furthermore, there is a significant difference between genders in the area of career growth.

Key words: Employee Engagement, Career Growth, Work-life Balance, Corporate Social Responsibility

1. INTRODUCTION

Current job conditions across the globe is rapidly changing and very competitive. The recent decades are full with technology innovation, development and improvement, all these aspects are related to the competitive market. Employee engagement is very crucial in a business however many organizations did not put much attention on its influences to the overall business success. There are numbers of authors found that employee that is highly engaged with the company can gradually change the company to become better in productivity, innovation, encouraging greater collaboration internally and externally (Mansor, Jaharudin & Nata, 2018). By retaining and attracting young talents in the country or other country, employee engagement can play a major role. Beheshti (2019)'s research shows that highly engaged teams perform 21% greater in terms of

profit to the organization, therefore, employee engagement is an essential driver that lead the organization to success.

According to the Labour Force Survey Report Malaysia 2014 published by the Department of Statistic Malaysia, the report shows an approximate 60% of total working adults in Malaysia are the generation Y, and it is increasing gradually (The Office of Chief Statistician Malaysia 2015). Generation Y is slowly joining the workplace; they are people who born between year 1980 –1994 (Curtin, 2019). They are the people who dominate the current work place and becoming the largest sources of talents in the current world. Generation Y is a generation that grew up with technology, for example, they use smart phones, laptops, and different gadgets in their daily lives, and it is also merging into the work environment (Kane, 2019). They prefer flexible schedules and a work-life

balance lifestyle. Generation Y are adults with high expectation to the company; they are dare to challenge at work, and able to accept authority (Kane, 2019). Other than that, Kane (2019) found out generation Y would not want to make mistakes of the previous generation, like the generation X and baby boomers. Generation Y is high in confident level, ambitious and achievement-oriented.

Generation Y is different from the previous generation - baby boomers and generation X; as generation Y show different approach to employers, companies, superiors in the working world (Kopertynska & Kmiolek, 2015). Despite the high rate of unemployment, if young people like generation Y did not receive what they have expected in the job, they will still quit the company. Young employees will stay longer in an organization if the condition of the work suits them. The basic difference between the generations of employees are the employee's expectation, employee's attitude towards their work, duties and responsibility, superiors and co-workers (Kopertynska & Kmiolek, 2015).

According to Holston-Okac & Mushi (2018), their research results show that employee's satisfaction towards their work, the compensation, employee engagement, work's motivation, and work environment are significant factors related to employee turnover intention. Generation Y are employees who born between year 1980 – 1994, they have been constantly criticized for having a leisurely attitude towards work and have a lower work engagement than generation X (Ying, Ahmad, Mohamed & Padlee, 2017). Ying, Ahmad, Mohamed & Padlee (2017) mentioned that more than 50% of high positioned employees agreed that they faced challenges in retaining the generation Y and many companies do not know the correct ways to engage their talented employees. The human resources management stated that employee engagement with the organization and the employee's attitude facing turnover issue is an important aspect (Biswakarma, 2015). The January 2017 key statistics of Labour Force in Malaysia showed the unemployment rate of January 2017 was 0.1% points higher than January 2016 (Mahidin, 2017).

As reported in "The 2017 Trends in Global Employee Engagement Report" Malaysia is the country that has the lowest employee engagement among 7 countries in Asia (Mah, 2017). The report stated that employee engagement scores for India were (69%), followed by China (67%), Thailand (65%), Philippines (65%), Indonesia (61%), Singapore (59%) and Malaysia (59%) (Mah, 2017). The studies also stated that employees working in Malaysia are less likely to recommend the company to their friends, and also less motivation towards their work (Mah, 2017). Low employee engagement can lead to low productivity of the employee that leads to organization negativity (Patro, 2013). Employee will most likely only do their job just to get the salary, and does not care about the business. As the problem of low employee engagement is the significant factor that can influence employee turnover in an organization (Holston-Okac & Mushi, 2018); this research is going to investigate whether the three variables career growth, work-life balance & corporate social responsibility can affect employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley.

1.1 Significance of research

This research aims to investigate the factors that can influence employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley, Malaysia. As employee engagement is an essential element in a business success. This study is carried out because research shows that Malaysia is one of the countries in Asia that has the lowest employee engagement in organizations. This study allows the employer to find out the way to engage their employee better. This study will also allow the employers to find out the accurate and practical strategies that can help to engage generation Y in their organization. By testing the factors career growth, work-life balance and corporate social responsibility towards employee engagement, the organization can understand and reflect employee feelings towards their work condition and the organization. As Generation Y - those who were born between year 1980 – 1994; is slowly becoming the major part of the workforce, this study will be important for the employers to identify how to engage the young talents in an organization.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Employee Engagement

According to previous literatures, employee engagement is defined in various method. Employee engagement which can affect workplace motivation can be separated into three dimensions - psychological meaningfulness, psychological safety, and psychological availability (Chaudhary, 2019 in citing Kahn, 1990). These psychological aspects can also contribute to the employee's personal engagement or disengagement at the workplace.

Psychological meaningfulness has been defined as "the value of a work goal or purpose, judged in relation to an individual's own ideals or standards" (Chaudhary, 2019 in citing May, 2004). People feel meaningfulness when they contribute effort that is not taken for granted and the contribution is beneficial to the organization (Chaudhary, 2019 in citing Kahn, 1990). Meaningfulness of work is an important attitude for employee engagement (Chaudhary, 2019 in citing Glavas & Kelly, 2014). The engagement in meaningful job affects in a better engagement, innovation and output (Chaudhary, 2019 in citing Csikszentmihalyi, 2003).

Psychological safety is defined as "feeling able to show and introduce themselves without scared of negative effect to personal image, position, or work" (Chaudhary, 2019 in citing Kahn, 1990). In other terms, the degree of trust in management decide the level of personal engagement in work (Chaudhary, 2019). The employee feels safe and secure when the management is helpful and supportive.

Psychological availability refers to the feeling of having physical, emotional or cognitive resources to engage the employee at work (Chaudhary, 2019 in citing Kahn, 1990). Psychological availability is the improvement of self-esteem and alignment of self-concept with the organization enables employees to perform their best self at work. According to Chaudhary (2019), people will join themselves with popular groups to build up their self-concept.

Following the work from Wahlberg, Ramalho & Brochado (2017), they have cited the work from Schaufeli (2002), which explains that employee engagement 'is characterized by vigour, dedication and absorption'. The first dimension, vigour, is

'high levels of energy and mental toughness during work, the willingness to spend effort in one's work and persistence even when difficult situations. Dedication refers to employees being strongly involved in their work and experiencing 'a sense of significance, enthusiasm, inspiration, pride, and challenge' (Wahlberg, Ramalho & Brochado, 2017). Finally, absorption is characterized by 'being fully concentrated and deeply focus in the individual's work, whereby time passes quickly and the individual is not willing to leave the work aside. (Wahlberg, Ramalho & Brochado, 2017).

Researcher found that hotel employees' engagement level can be improved by providing them training and reward management (Wahlberg, Ramalho & Brochado, 2017). Employees who works vigorously, delicately and immersed towards their job will produce positive outcomes, such as high level of job performance, employee commitment towards the organization and employee's job satisfaction. Engaged employees are able to deal with challenging tasks because they are passionate to their job and have a great connection with their job and organization. Employees are also less likely to leave the organization when they are engaged with the work and organization. This can be explained because they put in their cognitive, emotional and physical energy simultaneously in the full performance of their role; for service industry employees, they are pleased to deliver superior service quality and make customers satisfied by go beyond their formal job-related responsibilities (Wahlberg, Ramalho & Brochado, 2017).

Aktar (2016) define employee engagement as the extent of employees' commitment built on their physical, cognitive and emotional attachment with an organization and its value to achieve organizational goal. Employee engagement starts at the individual level constructs and outcome only then affect the organizational-level performance; this can be explained by an engaged employee enhances his/her job satisfaction, and the individual will work happily and improve the work performance, when work performance is fulfilled, it will positively affect the organizational goal. Therefore, reaching the organizational goal starts with an engaged employee that willing to achieve high performance. It can be concluded that employee is the main part of the organization's success (Aktar 2016).

2.2 Career Growth

Traditionally, a successful career was reflected by reaching a higher position in an organization hierarchy (Lee, Kwon, Kim & Cho, 2016). However, in the modern days, the employers and the employee have revised the expectations of long-term employment due to the factor of decreasing in job security and increasing in job mobility (Lee, Kwon, Kim & Cho, 2016). Career growth is the chance for employee to achieve more knowledge, skills and experience in an organization. The elements involve taking challenging assignments, learning opportunities and in-charge more job responsibilities in an organization. Career growth for the employees involves training on new ability, changing the job scope to a more advance level to attract and retain employees (Bai & Liu, 2018).

Intra-organizational growth and inter-organizational growth as ways of career growth. Intraorganizational career growth focused the motion of individual career advancement within the organization. Inter-organizational career growth focuses the growth of the employee on experience and skills that obtain in an organization (Bai & Liu, 2018).

Chandani, Mehta, Mall & Khohtar (2016) stated that engaged employees are those that the organisations provide opportunities for them to obtain new skills, learn new abilities, increase their wisdom to reach their potential. The researchers also stated that career growth practises help organisations retain smart employees and provide personal development opportunities (Chandani, Mehta, Mall & Khohtar 2016). Employees tend to stay, contribute their full efforts, and attached with organizations that invest in them by providing opportunities for their career growth (Chandani, Mehta, Mall & Khohtar 2016). Employers can improve employee's career growth by conducting training and develop their skills; it can allow employee to become more engage with the company; engaged employee also shows more respect to the organization (Chandani, Mehta, Mall & Khohtar 2016). Employee feels the company care of their growth which positively affect the employee to do extra-mile for the company.

Osborne & Hammoud (2017) mentioned that employees have proper growth and development channels could better select a career development

way to achieve their growth needs. Osborne & Hammoud (2017) stated that a company with effective employee engagement strategies can lead to business success, employee engagement and sustaining profitability. Leadership support can be one of the way or channels that improve employee engagement and job performance. Osborne & Hammoud (2017) suggestion is conducting an employee survey to find out the employees' expectation over time in an organization; the organization can also know whether the employee is having growth in their career, because a large organization might miss out focusing on some employees.

According to Bai & Liu (2018), their research result shows that career growth has a positive influence on employee engagement. They indicate that when employee has fast growth in their career, the higher the employee work engagement. Bai & Liu (2018)'s research findings shows that employees are able to attach to an organization if they are given career growth; employees are also found to form a strong sense of belonging and responsibility towards the organization. Employee will provide and invest their passion and energy into their work and highly engaged with the company. When employee improve their performance in their work, they will eventually develop new job skills, enhance professional abilities and accomplishments, and achieve their professional goals (Bai & Liu, 2018).

Liu, He & Yu (2016) has conducted a research on career growth show positive influence on employee engagement; if the organization would like to retain a constant high level of employee engagement, career growth has to come as the first factor that affect employee engagement. Employers should provide the employees with economic, power, abilities and social emotion's need. Sufficient resources given to the employee will affect the employee to be pleased to stay long in the organization and show high level of engagement (Liu, He & Yu, 2016).

Beygi, Kharazmi & Rahnama (2017) research results shows that career growth has a positive influence on employee engagement; their recommendations are managers should identify goal progress of the employees, provide learning opportunities, new knowledge and skills and help employees to achieve them. According to their

research findings, job engagement will increase by career growth; it is suggested that organization that improve career growth will lead to higher level of job engagement. The impact of job resources on job engagement will be accelerated and finally job engagement will increase more. It is also suggested that appropriate rewards for employee's achievement can improve job engagement.

According to Greenhaus, Peng & Allen (2012), some workers choose easier workloads and less promising positions in the industry to obtain a work and life balance, due to the factor of higher workloads lead to higher stress and job responsibility (as cited by Lee, Kwon, Kim & Cho 2016). These studies show that career growth not necessary lead to employee engagement, employee might avoid career advancement for an easier and work-life balance lifestyle. Lee, Kwon, Kim & Cho (2016)'s research findings shows that career growth of elderly employees did not foresee work engagement; the elderly employees are at the end of the career life that makes them uninterested to seek for job promotions.

2.3 Work-life balance

According to Sirgy & Lee (2018), work life balance is defined to which the balance of psychological energy and duration of time spend on work and non-work life that can satisfy one's need. Tetteh & Attiogbe (2019) defined work-life balance as the degree to which a person is able to concurrently balance the temporal, emotional and behavioural demands of work and personal life responsibilities. In other explanations, work-life balance can be explained by having an equal level achieved by an employee of work and non-work activities (Tetteh & Attiogbe, 2019). Work-life balance is defined to refer to one's assessment of their capabilities to well manage and carry out the responsibilities related to work, family, relationship and work (Cahill, McNamara, Pitt-Catsouphes & Valcour, 2015).

Tetteh & Attiogbe (2019) in their research concluded that when students combine full/part time work with education, it will negatively affect the quality of their education. They concluded that it's difficult to fulfil the demand of work and studies at the same time due to several challenges, like time constraint to study due to job requirements. This can lead to a low employee engagement for the people to work in an organization because time constraint

and tiredness are avoiding them to focus and work extra mile on their job (Tetteh & Attiogbe, 2019).

According to Sirgy & Lee (2018), a great work-life balance can effect in a high level of employee engagement that leads to goal attainment of an individual; an individual need to fulfil the successions of positive skills, values, privileges and status in their work then it can affect the other roles in their non-work life domain. Engaged employee will generate their balance of work and life, it will result in a better satisfaction with health, life and work (Cain, Busser & Kang, 2018). An individual's work-life balance can affect life satisfaction, and lead to longer lifespan, better work productivity and work satisfaction (Cain, Busser & Kang, 2018).

Wahlberg, Ramalho & Brochado (2017)'s study stated that employee that is engaged is more energetic, passionate and convincing the relationship with their work life and personal life, and they can recognize the demand of their jobs. Employee engagement towards their work has been shown to be beneficial to family satisfaction, an employee can recover from their work easily when there is engagement with the organization and their work (Hamilton Skurak, Malinen, Naswall & Kuntz, 2018). According to Hamilton Skurak, Malinen, Naswall & Kuntz (2018), work-life balance is more common to found in high work holism and engaged employees.

Cain, Busser & Kang (2018) research shows that work-life balance has a strong positive relationship with employee engagement; employee that has the ability to spend their own personal time and work time are more engaged to the organization. They also stated that engaged employee has self-establish positive feedback and positive attitude towards their work. In addition, employee engagement can be affected directly and indirectly of the work-home exchanges, this explains a person's gratification in their personal life will have an exchange of satisfaction in their work. Engaged employee is more enthusiastic in their work.

Shah, Mohd & Khairudin (2017)'s research result shows that work-life balance has significant impact to employee engagement. They stated that when an employee experiences better worklife balance, they will be more responsibility towards their work and more engaged with the organization (Shah, Mohd & Khairudin 2017). Shah, Mohd &

Khairudin (2017) research result matches with past literatures, which states that work-life balance policies can allow to improve employee engagement and it should be supported by the organization culture which is the beliefs, values and norms of the whole members from all levels.

According to Iqbal, Zia-ud-Din, Arif, Raza & Ishtiaq (2017), work-life balance had an influence on employee engagement of bank sector's employees; their recommendation of the study is organization should develop a supportive environment for the employees to maintain the worklife balance and lead to employee engagement. Following the research of Larasati & Hasanati (2018) based on "the effect of work-life balance towards employee engagement in Millennial generation"; the research results show that the employee engagement in Millennial Generation can be influenced by work-life balance. The hypothesis has come out with a result that if there is higher work-life balance, the employee engagement will be higher. Work-life balance is explained by the balance time spend on personal life and work life. Some important factors that can affect work-life balance of millennial generations are salaries, recognition of individuals, working hours that are flexible and career advancement. They found that work-life balance achievement includes reducing absenteeism, effective work, and employee retention (Larasati & Hasanati 2018).

Alvi, Ijaz Cheema & Haneef (2014)'s research on "Work life balance and employee job engagement exist in banking sector of Pakistan" showed that work-life balance can affect employee's work engagement. They concluded that work-life balance is crucially important in engaging employee of banking sector in Pakistan. They also suggested that employees are able to perform better performance in their duties when they live a work and life balance lifestyle, not only that, dedicated and devoted employee will be produced in a company that applies work-life balance.

2.4 Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is defined as voluntarily action carry out by an organization; the purpose of CSR is to meet and go beyond the expectation of the stakeholders by conforming social, ethical and environmental care together with the organization's revenue, profit, and legal responsibility (Kweyama, Cassim, Munapo &

Mutambara, 2015). CSR is explained as an organization's voluntary activities that contribute to the well-being of the public. CSR allows an increase in emotional connection between the employee and the organization; it helps to affect the employee to put extra effort in their work (Kweyama, Cassim, Munapo & Mutambara, 2015).

According to Chaudhary & Akhouri (2018), intrinsic CSR is referred to employees' justice perception on how they are treated and also how the organization treats the external parties. Employees will react how they feel towards the CSR actions even when they are not joined in these activities. Employee's attitudes are affected by the fairness of the activities towards themselves and other stakeholders. According to them, when an organization join CSR activities with the reason of their intrinsic desire to assist the community, employee will also feel that they will be treated well. Organization that involve with CSR activities due to ethical and moral reasons can also influence employee's opinion towards organization's respect for human honour. Moreover, Chaudhary & Akhouri (2018)'s research results show a positive relationship between intrinsic CSR and employee engagement. However, their research shows that extrinsic CSR did not have relationship with employee engagement.

According to Esmacelnezhad, Boerhannoeddin & Singaravelloo (2015), they have followed Carroll's Pyramid (1979) theory to explain CSR, it is categorized into four aspects, which are organization's economic, legal, ethical and discretionary responsibilities. The first aspect is economic, it is explained as establish new products and service, facilitate innovation and technological progress, find out new resources, provide fair wages for employee, and promising shareholders and owners with return on the investment. The second aspect is the legal responsibilities; it involves legal commitment expectations and requires the organization to fulfil their economic missions within the framework of legal responsibility, requirement and demand. The third aspect is ethical responsibilities; it is not a responsibility that systematized into the law; however, it is related to the approaches, practices, rules and action that are expected or disallowed by the individuals of the society. The last aspect is discretionary responsibility; discretionary responsibilities are a

type that society has no clear business strategy over them left as optional individual choices. Esmaeelinezhad, Boerhannoeddin & Singaravelloo (2015)'s research results show that economic and legal responsibilities show negative relation with employee engagement towards their work; however, ethical and discretionary responsibilities show positive relation to employee work engagement.

The research result carried out by Kweyama, Cassim, Munapo & Mutambara (2015) stated CSR is positively related to employee engagement. Engaged employee will react in way that facilitate the benefit of an organization and influence the outcome of business. Employee that felt engaged with the affection of CSR will affect the organization and individual work performance, pride and belief in the organization, career development opportunities and relationship with co-worker and supervisor (Kweyama, Cassim, Munapo & Mutambara, 2015). If CSR practices are carried out accordingly, employee engagement can be reinforced by giving the employee the feeling of a larger corporate mission and vision, and the organization share their values, and by helping them, will help to increase their own social connections (Kweyama, Cassim, Munapo & Mutambara, 2015).

According to Tsourvakas & Yfantidou (2018)'s research result, it shows CSR is related to employee engagement. Tsourvakas & Yfantidou (2018)'s finding suggests that employees will give their extra effort in their work if their company care for the society. Job engagement is explained by the researcher that proud, commitment and faithful to the job can relate to employee engagement; the researchers predict that the respondents in their research are gratified to recognize themselves with organization that have a caring image.

According to Peong (2019)'s research, it is found that CSR has a positive and significant influence on employee engagement. Their research is based on Tirta Komodo Regional Water Company, East Nusa Tenggara (Peong, 2019). They have concluded that organization has the duty to act ethically to their stakeholders, and also utilize positive actions that include responsibility in environmental, economic and social aspects (Peong 2019). CSR activities are one of the major

factors that affect employee engagement so that company's performance and effectiveness on work are guaranteed, not only that, it can also improve the company's reputation and economy (Peong, 2019).

Chaudhary (2017)'s research results show that CSR towards employees has influence on employee engagement at work. According to Chaudhary (2017), organization with flexible and worker friendly policies, fair and transparent processes, career development opportunities will provide staff with the extent to which they are supported and cared of by their organisation. These methods can improve the trust of the employees towards the company, and they will be more engaged towards their work and company; CSR towards staff will improve the self-esteem and organizational identification, it focused on the welfare of staff enhances the organization's favourable external image as an employer of choice. Other than that, Chaudhary (2017)'s research also shows that CSR activities towards the customer can affect employee engagement. CSR targeted at third parties are likely to affect workers' perceptions of personal justice and thus have an effect on their level of workplace engagement.

However, Chaudhary (2017) discovered that CSR had no significant effect on the level of employee engagement in external aspects such as culture, natural environment, future generations and non-governmental organisations. The reason behind this result is employee might think that company actions directed towards these types of stakeholders are part of their responsibilities and company's regular function, and it does not help to increase employee engagement, because it is not classified as additional responsibility.

Ferreira & Real de Oliveira (2014) found that CSR towards external stakeholders had no significant impact on employee engagement. They explained that employees might not know the company's CSR effort towards external stakeholders due to improper communication in work place. Not only that, employee might not aware whether the organization follow the legal regulations or pay taxes on time, however, employee will only know the CSR activities direct to them or the customers as they are involve in these actions in the daily operation. Employees will not know the CSR towards the external stakeholder

unless the organization put extra efforts to communicate and popularize their involvement in CSR activities directed towards these sets of stakeholders (Ferreira & Real de Oliveira, 2014).

Unlike other mentioned researches' results above, Ma (2011) found that CSR has no influence on employee engagement. The researcher found that when comparing other drivers of employee engagement which are senior management concern for employee well-being; opportunities for employees to improve skills and capabilities; input into department's decision making; career advancement opportunities; organization's ability to quickly resolve customers' concerns; and employees benefits to CSR, CSR is not an important driver to affect employee engagement. Most respondents disagree that they feel engaged with their job or company when their company has a strong CSR reputation. CSR can allow an organization to stand out from its competitor, but it cannot affect employee engagement. Ma (2011) stated that engaged employees can be proud of the organization; however, employee that feel pride in their organization might not necessarily be engaged. Other factors like commitment, motivation and passion might be needed to engage employee in an organization (Ma, 2011).

3. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

Figure 2.1: Proposed area of research

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This research has used descriptive research. The reason is to know the relationship and the affect between the factors (career growth, work-life balance & corporate social responsibility) and employee engagement of the generation Y in Klang Valley. Quantitative research method was used for data collection to investigate the influence of career growth, work-life balance & corporate social responsibility towards employee engagement of the generation Y in Klang Valley, Malaysia. It was a cross sectional study where the data was collected once at a particular time.

3.2 Sampling Design

Non-probability sampling technique was used in this study. Researcher had used convenient sampling falls under non-probability sampling to examine the data of this study. Convenient sampling was defined as an easily accessible process for the researcher to collect data from the population.

The target population for this research were Generation Y who born between 1980 – 1994 (Curtin, 2019). The respondents had to be staying in Klang Valley. According to Kuala Lumpur Population (2019), Klang Valley was an estimated urban agglomeration of 7.2 million in 2016; the population who born between 1980 – 1994 is at 2.31 million. Data collection was done through online survey whereby a questionnaire was developed and distributed to 400 respondents.

3.3 Instrumentation

Data for in this study, questionnaire was used as a research tool. The questionnaires were conducted in a close-ended form. It was constructed into five parts, Section A: Demographic Profile, Section B: Employee Engagement, Section C: Career Growth, Section D: Work-life Balance and Section E: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Section A consisted of questions regarding whether the respondent was residing in Klang Valley, the respondent's year of birth, whether the respondent was currently working in an organization, gender and marital status. While section B, section C, section D and section E were measured by a 5-point Likert Scale, ranging from strongly disagree (1); disagree (2); neutral (3); agree (4) and strongly agree (5).

The result revealed that the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for all the variables tested were relatively high: employee engagement (0.748), career growth (0.836), work-life balance (0.732) and corporate social responsibility (0.734).

3.4 Hypothesis of the study

H₁: Career growth has a significant influence on employee engagement among Generation Y

H₂: Work-life balance has a significant influence on employee engagement among Generation Y

H₃: Corporate social responsibility (CSR) has a significant influence on employee engagement among Generation Y.

3.4 Assumptions of Parametric

Before choosing a statistical test to apply to the data collected, the researcher addressed the issue of whether the data are parametric or not. Statistical tests are used to analyse some aspect of a sample. The assumptions of parametric were met when: sample data are continuous and measurements met the minimum sample size requirement (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016), the ratio of cases/samples (N) to variables (IV) exceeded 5:1 (Osborne and Costello, 2002), more than 70 percent of the questionnaire can be measured using scale, there was a linear relationship among the two variables and data collected were normally distributed based on the results obtained from the normality test conducted.

3.5 Statistical Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaires were analysed through a series of statistical test. The data collected were analysed using the SPSS statistical analysis software for Windows. The statistical procedures for quantitative research include reliability analysis, normality test, descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation and multiple regression analysis and T-test.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis was used to analyse the targeted respondents' demographic information using frequency and percentage. The basic information of respondents was highly important because it helped us to know who were the ones contributing value to the research. The general information included: gender and marital status. There are total of 244 male participants, and 156 female participants, which accumulate a total of 400 respondents. There are 346 (86.5%) respondents are on single status, and 54 (13.5%) respondents are on married status

4.2 Pearson's Correlation Analysis

Table 4.1 Correlation Analysis

Variable	1	2	3	4
<i>1. Employee Engagement</i>	-			
<i>2. Career Growth</i>	.775**	-		
<i>3. Work-life Balance</i>	.583**	.599**	-	
<i>4. Corporate Social Responsibility</i>	.662**	.753**	.721**	-

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

The results of Pearson’s Correlation Analysis on the study are as shown in Table 4.1. Based on the results, it proves that there are significant relationships between the dependent variable (employee engagement) and the independent variables (career growth, work-life balance and corporate social responsibility).

Career growth has a strong correlation ($r = 0.775, p < 0.05, N = 400$). Work-life balance has the moderate correlation ($r = 0.583, p < 0.05, N = 400$). Corporate social responsibility has the strong correlation ($r = 0.662, p < 0.05, N = 400$).

4.3 Multiple Regression Analysis

4.3.1 Model Summary

Table 4.2 Regression Analysis: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.790 ^a	.625	.622	.19092

a. Predictors: (Constant), Corporate Social Responsibility, Work-life Balance, Career Growth

According to Table 4.2, the computed R-square was at 0.625, which also indicated as 62.5%. This showed that career growth, work-life balance and corporate social responsibility accounted for 62.5% of the variation in employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley. While 37.5% of the variance in factors that affect employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley remained as unknown factors.

4.3.2 Analysis of Variance

Table 4.3 Regression Analysis: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.036	3	8.012	219.801	.000 ^b
	Residual	14.435	396	.036		
	Total	38.471	399			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Engagement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Corporate Social Responsibility, Work-life Balance, Career

According to Table 4.3, a significant regression equation as $[F (3,396) = 219.801, p < 0.05]$ was built. Since the amount of significance is less than 0.05, this demonstrates that the conceptual framework can be adopt and is suitable for the results.

4.3.3 Coefficients

Table 4.4 Regression Analysis: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.787	.155		5.063	.000
<i>Career Growth</i>	.575	.044	.619	13.125	.000
<i>Work-life Balance</i>	.152	.046	.147	3.276	.001
<i>Corporate Social Responsibility</i>	.095	.057	.091	1.667	.096

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Engagement

According to Table 4.4, it shows the β -value and significance level for each independent variable.

The result shows that career growth has a positive influence on employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley, ($\beta = 0.619$, $p < 0.05$, $N = 400$). Career growth has a significant level of ($p = 0.001$), which is less than 0.05. Therefore, H1 is not rejected. The result is similar to Bai & Liu (2018); Liu, He & Yu (2016); Beygi, Kharazmi & Rahnama (2017) research, which show that career growth has influence on employee engagement.

The result shows that work-life balance has a positive influence on employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley, ($\beta = 0.147$, $p < 0.05$, $N = 400$). Work-life balance has a significant level of ($p = 0.001$), which is less than 0.05. Therefore, H2 is not rejected. The result is in line with Shah, Mohd & Khairudin (2017); Iqbal, Zia-ud-Din, Arif, Raza & Ishtiaq (2017); Larasati & Hasanati (2018); Alvi, Ijaz Cheema & Haneef (2014)'s research, which show that work-life balance has influence on employee engagement.

The result shows that corporate social responsibility has no influence on employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley, ($\beta = 0.091$, $p < 0.05$, $N = 400$). Corporate social responsibility has a significant level of ($p = 0.096$), which is more than 0.05. Therefore, H3 is rejected. The result is similar to Chaudhary (2017); Ma (2014); Ferreira & Real de Oliveira (2014) research which show that corporate social responsibility has no influence on employee engagement.

Figure 4.1: Summarized Result

4.4 Independent sample t-test

		Group Statistics					
What is your gender?		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean		
Career Growth	Female	156	4.42	.419	.034		
	Male	244	4.44	.266	.017		

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Equal variances assumed		5.098	.024	-.640	398	.523	-.02194	.03430
Equal variances not assumed				-.582	235.237	.561	-.02194	.03768

A *t*-test revealed a statistically reliable difference between the mean number of career growth that the Male (M= 4.44, s= 0.266) and Female has (M= 4.42, s= 0.419), *t*(398), *p*= 0.024, *α*=0.05

5. CONCLUSION

In this research, to identify whether career growth can be an influencing factor towards employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley is the first objective. This objective has been met by using multiple regression analysis, and the result shows there is an influence of career growth on employee engagement.

The second objective is to identify whether work-life balance can influence employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley. This objective has also been met by using multiple regression analysis, and the result shows there is an influence of work-life balance on employee engagement.

Lastly, the third objective is to identify whether corporate social responsibility can influence employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley. This objective has been met by using multiple regression analysis, and the result shows there is no influence of corporate social responsibility on employee engagement.

In addition to that, there is a significant difference between genders in the dimension of career growth among Generation Y.

5.1 Implications

Results show that there is an influence of career growth towards employee engagement. The results highlight the importance of career growth among Generation Y in Klang Valley when employee engagement is being considered. Organisations should be aware of this and put more effort into ensuring career growth is evident in an organisation. To achieve that, better human resources planning and employee performance management system should be implemented. When employees are aware and are satisfied with the career growth in an organisation, employee engagement will also be sustained. Aside from that, results also indicate a significant difference between gender and career growth. As such, organisations should address the differences in attitude of their employees towards career growth so that expectation of the employees and goal attainment in career growth can be fulfilled.

Work-life balance is also found to be an important factor that leads to employee engagement among Generation Y in the workforce. As work-life balance involves perceive fairness and balance

between work and personal time, organisations should be aware of this and avoid from cultivating a working culture where work-life balance is not maintained. A better human resources planning will yet again be useful to ensure work-life balance among employees. Work should be redesigned to allow employees to be able to perform better which will lead to an increase in performance and efficiency. Company policies should also be reviewed to ensure that organisational culture encourages work-life balance instead of discouraging work-life balance such as excessive overtime or bring work back home.

Lastly, corporate social responsibility is found to not significantly influence employee engagement among Generation Y. The results obtained should not discourage organisations from actively involved in corporate social responsibilities. Instead, companies should further promote good corporate social responsibility practices among their employees and place higher amount of effort to educate employees about the benefits of such a practice. Employees should perceive corporate social responsibility practices to be intrinsically driven instead of extrinsically driven.

5.2 Limitation and Future Research

The first limitation in this research is the target generation. Generation Y is targeted in this research, and it is the respondent who born between year 1980 – 1994. However, there are also other few generations that are not investigated in this research, example as baby boomers who born between 1944 – 1964, generation X who born between 1965 – 1979, and generation Z who born between 1995 – 2015 (Curtin 2019). Future researchers can investigate the factors that affect employee engagement on other generations.

The second limitation is the location. The researcher concentrated solely on respondents residing in Klang Valley, Malaysia. Other areas in Kuala Lumpur are not covered in this research. Not only that, other nations in Malaysia and other countries did not generalize the outcomes. Future researcher can conduct the research in other area in Kuala Lumpur, other states in Malaysia and also other countries. The people live in other areas can have different opinion on this research topic, therefore, it is suggested to future researcher to conduct this research in other places in order to gather more findings.

The third limitation is the language used. This research was presented in English. Although English is an international language used by most of the people, there are still people that couldn't understand or read English language. Therefore, people that cannot understand or read English cannot complete the questionnaire. Future researchers may generate comparable studies in distinct languages. This can overcome the barrier of language for different language people.

The fourth limitation is the R-square value found in the regression analysis. The R-square value computed is at 0.625 (62.5%). This explains that the independent variables have only explained 62.5% of the dependent variable in overall. The remaining 37.5% of the variance is unknown factors. Future researchers can find out other factors that can affect employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley. Future researchers may investigate on empowerment, compensation, and organisational culture. Other than that, independent variable – corporate social responsibility was found no influence on employee engagement of generation Y in Klang Valley. People in other area might have different opinion. Therefore, future researcher can investigate this factor in other area of Kuala Lumpur or other states in Malaysia.

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